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“SHE WHO STANDS”

She wakes before sunrise,
A whispered prayer before she cooks the rice,
Folds the beddings, wraps her head,
Preparing for the day ahead.

A Strong mind with a fragile heart,
A cup of hope, she sips, she starts,
Wearing courage, holding pride,
Bruises hidden deep inside.

When loneliness comes, she stands up high,
Responsibilities and bonds once made her cry.
Though silent storms rage deep inside,
Still, she stands and does not hide.

Pain and woe are often the price,
For love and its burning fire,
The peace of home and a wealthy life,
Are all that she desires.